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**“EMERGING CHALLENGES AND ISSUES
CONCERNING INTERNATIONAL CYBER LAWS”**

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ABSTRACT

The technological development has considerably changed in the world at large. Today the cyber space witnessed great changes in the field of information technology. The rapid changes in the information technology tend to raise various challenges and issues in the future days like increased cybercrime, formulation of unique laws in international level and jurisdiction issues. Cyber space has no geographical boundary limits and it has given rise to different types of cybercrimes throughout the globe. International law is very much necessary to govern the cyberspace. All sovereign independent states possess jurisdiction within their territory, but cyber-crime mostly committed beyond the state jurisdiction in cyberspace. To maintain unique discipline in the cyberspace we need to enact an international cyber law. The dichotomy underlines the fact that there is a ‘tug-of-war’ between the state law and international law. It is very difficult to control and punish the cyber criminals based on state laws in certain crime. As the cybercrime is growing across the world, there is a need of enacting an appropriate cyber law to maintain the cyber security. In this paper, the study is mainly concentrated on the issues and challenges faced to enact the international cyber law in providing global jurisdiction to handle cybercrime.

Keywords: cyber space, cybercrime, dichotomy, cyber security.

Introduction

The modern life is reached to such an extent that even small child is not able to live without the use of technology. The technology has become an integral part of human life. The technological development has given rise to a cyber world constituting cyber space. There are rapid growth and changes is taking place every minute in the field of information technology and cyber space. It is always difficult to assume the future because future cannot be foreseen.

A man is a social animal and he cannot be perfected without the code of conduct. To control human activities and behaviour we need to have strict rules and regulation passed by the sovereign authority. To control and govern the human activities in the cyber world there is the necessity of cyber law. Since the cyber world is borderless, it's very difficult to control the cyber activities in the world at large. The different countries have different laws to control the cyber space, but the challenge is to have the unique international cyber law. There is very emerging requirement to enact the single uniform cyber law to control the cyber space. The territorial jurisdiction issues are affecting to enact the uniform cyber law at the world at large.

Meaning of Cyber Space

The term cyberspace was first time introduced by William Gibson in his book, "Neuromancer", 1984. cyberspace describes the flow of digital data through the network of interconnected computers.

Cyberspace is a domain characterised using electronics and the electromagnetic spectrum to store, modify, and exchange data via networked systems and associated physical infrastructures. In effect, cyberspace can be thought of as the interconnection of human beings through computers and telecommunication, without regard to physical geography. Cyberspace allows users to share information, interact, swap ideas, play games, engage in discussions or social forums, conduct business, and create intuitive media, among many other activities.

Emerging Challenge of International Cyber Laws

The rapid growth in the technologic world has cropped up with many challenges and problems in the world wide. Cyberspace has no limitations as to geographical boundaries which have given rise to increasing cybercrimes, which may affect any country across the globe. To control such a cyber space need to concentrate on governing laws in the world and it should be amended and adopted from time to time.

There is a need for entering into an international agreement between the countries to control the criminal

activities in the cyberspace. Globally, Various trends and challenges are likely to arise with the development of techno world.

Social Networking

The crime rate in the social media is rapidly increasing and moving beyond the control. The criminal activities in social media extended in such a way that it's very difficult to predict and control the problem. Moreover, here the major problem comes to apply the

legal rules of the nation. Cybercrime is increasing in by overtaking the existing cyber laws. The cyber jurisdiction issues are one of the major problems in the present day. The data shared through the social media has major security threats in the cyber space and it became a challenging task to protect the right to privacy.

Social media legal issues continue to be significant. To avoid social media crimes and protect the privacy related to social media, it is a challenge for cyber law makers across the world to not only provide appropriate legislative and regulatory mechanisms but also provide for effective remedies for redressal to the victims of various unauthorized, unwanted criminal activities done in cyber space and social media.

Mobile Phone and Smart Phone Usage

The usage of mobile phones or smart phones is more in India and China while comparing to another country. The increased usage of mobile devices is likely to give rise to more mobile related crimes. There is a need for appropriate enabling frameworks for the governance of mobile usage and control the mobile related crime in across the world.

Cyber Security

At present, the cyber security becomes a challenging issue in the world. The cybercrime is growing across the world without any break, so there is a need to have an appropriate statute to control these activities and protect the cyber security. The data stored in the cyber space is not having any security at the globe. To provide strong cyber security there is need to enact the intelligent and transparent international cyber law as a part of international law with the consent of all the participating countries.

Ethical Issues

The ethical hackers plays a pivotal role in controlling the crime and identifying the criminal. There is no adequate number of members who are trained and appointed to be an ethical hacker in the country. The

ratio of unethical hackers is more than the ethical hackers. There is another issue is no proper training for the legal enforcement bodies to play their effective role to control the cybercrime. Therefore, the government has the challenge to train and provide increasingly ethical hackers to the nation.

Cyber Jurisdiction

Cybercrime is paper less and boundary-less crime, it has no jurisdiction. The nation has its own jurisdiction and national laws are able to operate and control within its territory. The scope and limitation of cybercrime extent to the whole cyber space and jurisdiction

problem arise to apply the legal and remedial measures. Since the cyber space has a single jurisdiction, it's better to enact the uniform cyber law for the whole world to control the cyber space as one law.

Conclusion

In this paper, I have made a brief study regarding the challenges and issues in enacting globally accepted international cyber laws. As per my opinion, there is the immediate need to enact the international cyber law to control the activities cyber space. In my conclusion, I would like to suggest that the research community should concentrate and address the areas of cyber space to bring an effective remedy to control the cybercrime activities. Law alone may not be completely successful in controlling the cybercrime, so as a result even the legal enforcement authorities and staffs should be trained properly.

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